

Navigating AI: Challenges and opportunities for Swiss SMEs

Artificial intelligence (AI) offers Swiss SMEs numerous opportunities, such as increasing efficiency and productivity or gaining new insights from data. Simultaneously, challenges are also encountered, such as a lack of expertise or limited reliability.

This fact sheet provides information on relevant application cases for AI and also on obstacles and solutions when it is introduced. It provides practical advice and points to resources that make the difficulties allegedly encountered when starting with AI easier for SMEs.

How Swiss SMEs can successfully use AI

Swiss SMEs often face a dilemma when using AI tools such as ChatGPT and DeepL. Despite restrictions, these tools are widely used and a ban could be more risky than controlled use. A gradual introduction, clear governance and efficient collaboration will allow SMEs to reap the benefits of AI in order to drive growth, innovate and remain competitive. Committed employees and their training are crucial for safe and effective implementation. External expertise, strong partnerships and the utilisation of funding opportunities also play a key role in strategically tackling the challenges and achieving long-term success.

Steps to the successful introduction of AI:

- **Inform and evaluate requirements:**
Analyse business requirements and technological possibilities to find out in which areas AI can create added value.
- **Start with pilot projects:**
Start with small projects to test AI applications. This will help you to minimise risks and gain a better understanding of the practical benefits of AI.
- **Obtain expert advice:**
Collaborate with technology providers, educational and research institutions, and consultants to gain access to cutting-edge AI solutions and training.
- **Establish governance:**
Define guidelines for data protection, the data lifecycle and the ethical use of AI. In this way, you ensure competences and responsible implementation.

Read more about this topic in the detailed article by the SAIROP partners

Applications and examples of AI for SMEs

The following applications show how and where AI technologies are already being used today. The assessment refers to how complex their implementation is, from simple and moderate to difficult.

Content creation with AI

Tools such as Microsoft Copilot support text creation, translations and style optimization.

Example: In marketing or customer support, the processing time can be reduced by up to 50 %.

Education with AI

AI combined with VR/AR enables individual and practical learning.

Example: Employees are trained in realistic scenarios, e.g. for service tasks.

Image and video analysis

AI optimises quality controls or automates document processing.

Example: A catering company automated the processing of 30,000 invoices per month and increased accuracy.

AI in software development

AI-based assistants like Gemini facilitate code analysis, troubleshooting and documentation.

Example: JetBrains IntelliJ offers AI-supported functions for more efficient and higher-quality code development.

Decision-making with data science and machine learning

Algorithms analyse patterns in data to support decision-making.

Example: A company used machine learning (ML) to optimise personnel planning in logistics and increased efficiency by 15 %.

Optimisation in production and logistics

AI-supported algorithms improve delivery networks, forecasts and pricing.

Example: A beverage retailer automates orders for 600 stores and reduces overstocks and out-of-stock situations.

AI-supported language models with external knowledge

Large language models (LLM) can be supplemented by external data sources, such as company data. This combination improves the quality of the answers and reduces errors.

Example: A company's product information is searched when processing an inquiry and relevant details are used to provide more precise answers. Sources can be specified and false statements reduced.

Safety through ML

ML detects and prevents fraud, e.g. in online banking.

Example: Splunk uses ML for anomaly detection and failure prevention in IT systems.

Quality control with computer vision

Neural networks identify errors in real time, ideal for small batches and precision parts.

Example: A Swiss manufacturer uses AI to optimise tool production and achieve the highest quality standards.

Process optimisation

AI minimises downtimes through automated adjustment of production parameters.

Example: In the machining industry, start-up times for new products are significantly reduced by AI technology.

Predictive maintenance

AI recognises potential machine problems at an early stage and extends operating times.

Example: In the railroad industry, maintenance is carried out proactively to avoid breakdowns.

Challenges and solutions

- **Limited knowledge and costs:** A lack of knowledge about AI makes it difficult to evaluate resources.
Solution: Analyse data basis, promote further training.
- **Concerns among employees:** Worries about data protection and job loss are widespread.
Solution: Transparency, rules and team workshops.
- **Complexity and trust:** AI models are often “black boxes”.
Solution: Consider limitations and manage risks.
- **Automation errors:** Misinterpretations due to incorrect AI results.
Solution: Careful use case definition and employee training.
- **Lack of data:** A lack of representative training data makes model development more difficult.
Solution: If possible, start with simpler use cases, collect data in a targeted manner or generate it synthetically.
- **Stereotypes in AI:** Social biases in basic models.
Solution: Create awareness and expand knowledge.
- **Regulatory requirements:** Compliance with data protection laws or the EU AI Act may be complex.
Solution: Secure infrastructure and trained employees.

Do you need inspiration for your own AI project ideas? Are you looking for a research partner, advanced training or other services in the field of artificial intelligence? Visit SAIROP, the central platform for AI research and development in Switzerland, where you can access AI knowledge and innovation.

If you have any questions, please contact us through info@sairop.swiss

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(in English)

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Authors: Lamia Friha, UNIGE | Alain Hugentobler, UNIGE | Iason Kastanis, CSEM | Jana Koehler, HSLU | Manuel Kugler, SATW | Mascha Kurpicz-Briki, BFH | Gianfranco Moi, UNIGE | Andrea Rizzoli, IDSIA | Benjamin Sawicki, NCCR Automation | Gabriele Schwarz, Innovista Management GmbH

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